

A Spatio-Temporal Mapping of Solar Photovoltaic Diffusion in Southern Luxembourg (2019-2023)

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Summary

This study investigates how the visibility of photovoltaic (PV) installations influences the diffusion of adoption in the Esch-sur-Alzette region of Luxembourg from 2019 to 2023. By mapping PV trends using a convolutional neural network (CNN), the research highlights spatial clusters of adoption, particularly along visible roadways, suggesting that social diffusion—shaped by visibility—plays a crucial role in driving uptake. The findings indicate that while financial incentives are important, localised visibility and cultural factors significantly influence PV adoption, underscoring the need for policies that harness these dynamics to accelerate the transition in urban areas.

KEYWORDS: Solar photovoltaics, Convolutional Neural Network, Social Diffusion, Renewable Energy Transitions

1. Introduction

Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems offer a practical, grassroots approach to advancing partial energy independence and bolstering national energy security. Over the past decade, there has been a notable increase in PV adoption, driven by technological advancements and eco-conscious early adopters who have embraced these decentralised energy solutions. In Luxembourg, as well as across Europe, the past three years have seen a particularly rapid uptake of PV systems, largely propelled by the pursuit of energy price stability, affordability, and the availability of attractive subsidies. The recent energy crisis, exacerbated by geopolitical tensions and supply chain disruptions, has underscored the vulnerability of fossil-fuel-dependent energy systems. As energy prices fluctuate unpredictably, the push for greater self-sufficiency through decentralised renewable energy solutions has gained momentum. However, despite this urgency, adoption remains uneven across socio-economic groups and urban environments, necessitating a deeper investigation into the underlying barriers and policy interventions required to accelerate PV integration. However, progress is impeded by a range of challenges, including systemic issues such as inequitable national policies and incentive structures that often favour wealthier households, as well as personal factors like individual attitudes, worldviews, and confidence in using the technology. Research indicates that the visibility of residential solar PV installations can play a dual role in either promoting or hindering adoption, depending on the social and cultural context (Mundaca & Samahita, 2020; Rode & Müller, 2021).

Luxembourg lags behind its neighbouring countries in the adoption of renewable energy, with only 6.85% of its total energy derived from domestic renewable sources. Within this, solar energy

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contributes a mere 1.75% (Ritchie et al., 2022). Prior research indicates that just 4.1% of residential properties in Luxembourg have integrated solar PV systems, reflecting a sluggish uptake despite national and EU-level incentives (Skinner and Jones, 2024). This percentage is even lower in the case study area in the south-western region, where adoption is hindered by a combination of socio-economic and spatial factors, including lower income levels, high population transience, and the complexities of a dense urban landscape that restrict installation potential (Skinner and Jones, 2024).

Given the lack of openly accessible data documenting PV adoption, we undertook the development of a solar implementation cadastre for south-western Luxembourg spanning the 5-year period from 2019 to 2023. This time frame enables the identification of general adoption patterns while facilitating comparisons between the pre-crisis and current energy crisis contexts. The region's relatively low existing PV presence further positions it as fertile ground for examining the potential for future PV adoption without the confounding influence of extensive pre-2019 installations. By capturing these dynamics, the cadastre provides a foundation for targeted policy interventions and strategic planning to accelerate the region's energy transition, whilst also illustrating the role of peer effects in PV adoption. This study therefore, provides insights into whether heightened energy insecurity has translated into increased adoption rates and how policy interventions can be adjusted to enhance resilience in future crises.

2. Literature Overview

Temporal investigations into PV adoption were notably carried out by Bollinger and Gillingham (2012) whereby the peer effects in California were studied. It was concluded that solar panels adoption within the zip code increased the likelihood of PV adoption by 0.78% (Bollinger & Gillingham, 2012). However, temporal studies of PV diffusion have often taken place in data rich locations, leaving countries with strict privacy laws, or trans-regional studies having to look for alternative methods. The solution to this is to apply the usage of CNNs over sequential years to measure uptake and diffusion (Wang et al., 2022). Since 2017, Luxembourg has annually developed RGB orthoimagery of 10cm resolution, which has allowed for the development of a CNN to model to establish the status quo of residential solar PV in Luxembourg (Skinner and Jones, 2024).

Wang et al. (2022) also emphasised the potential of CNNs not only to map adoption trends but also to identify areas where visibility and social diffusion could amplify uptake. This aligns with evidence suggesting that visible solar installations can positively influence adoption in some contexts, while provoking resistance in others, depending on local aesthetics and cultural perceptions (Rode & Müller, 2021). The gap in the literature lies at the neighbourhood scale, where detailed investigations into how visibility interacts with urban form and socio-cultural factors to shape adoption remain sparse. Following our previous study, Luxembourg's southern canton of Esch-sur-Alzette was found to have a significantly lower amount of PV relative to the number of residential buildings (Skinner and Jones, 2024). This refined perspective is crucial for assessing the effectiveness of past interventions and guiding future strategies for PV adoption, particularly in underperforming regions.

While past research has examined PV adoption at regional and national scales, studies at the neighbourhood level remain scarce, particularly in data-restricted environments like Luxembourg. Existing literature primarily focuses on adoption trends in well-documented settings, often overlooking areas where privacy constraints limit access to household-level data. Furthermore, while peer effects and social visibility have been recognised as influential factors in adoption patterns, their interaction with urban density, socio-economic disparities, and policy structures has yet to be systematically explored. By leveraging high-resolution spatial data and CNN-based detection, this study bridges these gaps, offering a nuanced analysis of how PV diffusion is shaped by neighbourhood-scale characteristics.

The H3 hierarchical grid system allows for the neighbourhood scale to be analysed at different levels, whilst also allowing for investigations that are no longer limited to the constraints associated with

postcodes or infrastructure. It divides the globe into equally sized hexagons, offering an efficient and reliable method for indexing and querying vast geospatial data (Aini et al., 2023). By organising spatial data in this way, H3 enables scalable and accurate spatial analysis while maintaining consistency across different geographic areas (Aini et al., 2023).

3. Methodology

A convolutional neural network (CNN) model with an accuracy of 87% was employed to detect solar PV installations using 10 cm ground resolution RGB orthoimagery (public.data.lu) for each year from 2019 to 2023 across Luxembourg's canton of Esch-sur-Alzette. Using ArcGIS Pro's Deep Learning tools, the model was trained and validated using labelled PV polygons from seven contrasting communes in Luxembourg (Skinner and Jones, 2024). The model was then used iteratively from 2019 to 2023 over orthoimagery of the 11 communes in Luxembourg's southwestern region (200 km²). To assess model performance, a random number generator, in conjunction with the building's polygon OpenStreetMap (OSM) identification number, was used to evaluate detection accuracy. The detected PV installations were then attributed to their corresponding building polygons and integrated into H3 hexagonal grids at resolutions ranging from level 6 (36.2 km²) to level 10 (0.11 km²). This approach facilitated scalability while mitigating the modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP) associated with predefined neighbourhoods (Cabrera-Barona et al., 2016).

To analyse spatiotemporal trends, the results were aggregated into an emerging hot spot analysis, identifying patterns of PV adoption and assessing whether emerging hotspots influenced adoption trends in adjacent hexagons. This analysis was conducted both in absolute terms (number of buildings) and normalised by the number of buildings per hexagon to account for variations in urban density and ensure that adoption trends were not disproportionately driven by areas with higher building concentrations.

Global Moran's I and Local Anselin Moran's I (k=4) analyses were then applied to determine the presence of spatial autocorrelation. Global Moran's I assessed whether PV adoption exhibited a clustered, dispersed, or random spatial pattern across the study area, while Local Anselin Moran's I (LISA) identified statistically significant clusters and outliers.

Due to communes having different additional subsidy policies, an analysis of growth rates in each commune was carried out to determine if more favourable subsidies affected the number of PV adopters. Collectively, these methods provided a scalable and systematic framework for analysing the spatial and temporal dynamics of PV adoption, offering insights into how adoption hotspots evolve and interact with neighbouring areas, thus contributing to a deeper understanding of Luxembourg's solar energy transition.

4. Results

The results overwhelmingly indicate that adoption rates are clustered within certain areas, particularly along stretches of road where PV is more visible (see fig.1). These patterns were most prominently seen at the H9 level (0.11 km²) but could even be seen at the more refined H10 level (0.02 km²). From the spatial autocorrelation analyses, Global Moran's I (0.324, $p < 0.000001$) confirmed a strong, non-random pattern, with a z-score of 55.55 suggesting a less than 1% likelihood of random occurrence. Using inverse distance weighting and a 125.1m Euclidean threshold, adoption trends exhibited localised spatial dependence.

Figure 1 Growth of PV Installations between 2019 and 2023 in the canton of Esch-sur-Alzette. Inset map shows how trends follow certain road networks.

Figure 2: LISA map showing clusters of PV installation growth rates.

The LISA statistic (see fig.2) once again illustrates these clusters but also gives evidence that areas with similar land uses, such as suburban areas do not necessarily follow the same adoption trends, indicating that other factors, such as the diffusion of ideas through visibility may play a role in PV adoption.

PV adoption across the communes of Esch-sur-Alzette exhibited a steady increase from 2019 to 2023, with a marked acceleration following 2020 (see Fig. 3). This growth appears to be primarily driven by Luxembourg’s Klimabonus subsidies, which cover up to 62.5% of installation costs, particularly influencing uptake in suburban municipalities such as Mondercange and Käerjeng. Despite the disruptions caused by COVID-19, including initial supply chain challenges, the adoption rate remained resilient, with growth resuming strongly thereafter. In contrast, urban areas like Esch-sur-Alzette and Differdange experienced slower adoption, likely due to factors such as higher building density and the complexities associated with property ownership structures, as tenants are far less likely to adopt PV due to a lack of decision-making power, financial incentives, and direct benefits from energy savings. Dudelange, however, demonstrates an anomaly in this pattern, with growth primarily driven by the expansion of residential areas on the city’s outskirts. These trends highlight the efficacy of financial incentives in promoting PV adoption, while also revealing spatial disparities that point to the necessity for targeted policies aimed at boosting urban PV deployment and addressing adoption barriers in densely populated areas. Although the majority of PV installations are currently situated on larger commercial or industrial buildings, there is a noticeable increase in uptake within residential buildings. Consequently, future research will focus exclusively on residential PV adoption to determine whether these patterns differ substantially from broader trends.

Figure 3: Growth rates of PV installations by commune. Note that this does not distinguish between PV on commercial, industrial or residential buildings.

5. Conclusion

These findings underscore the spatial clustering of PV adoption, where visibility along key roads may influence diffusion. While financial incentives play a crucial role, adoption is shaped by more than just subsidies or land use patterns. Localised spatial dependence and visibility effects appear to be significant drivers, with urban areas facing barriers linked to density and ownership complexities, while suburban uptake varies despite similar land use. The study has certain limitations. Although spatial

correlations suggest visibility-driven diffusion, they do not directly capture social influence or household decision-making. The five-year timeframe provides insight into emerging trends but may not fully reflect long-term behavioural shifts or policy impacts. Moreover, the absence of data on building ownership and tenancy restricts a deeper understanding of adoption constraints in rented properties.

Despite these challenges, the methodology is adaptable to other regions with similar spatial data availability, offering a scalable tool for assessing PV diffusion. However, customised training datasets for orthoimagery are necessary to ensure accuracy. Future research should integrate socio-economic data, qualitative surveys, and temporal modelling to refine these insights. Policies aimed at increasing PV adoption should consider not only financial incentives but also visibility-driven strategies, particularly in urban areas where adoption remains constrained.

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References

- Accueil - Portail Open Data* (no date). Available at: <https://data.public.lu/fr/> (Accessed: 30 January 2025).
- Aini, A.N. *et al.* (2023) ‘An Enhanced Earthquake Risk Analysis using H3 Spatial Indexing’, *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1245(1), p. 012014. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1245/1/012014>.
- Bollinger, B. and Gillingham, K. (2012) ‘Peer Effects in the Diffusion of Solar Photovoltaic Panels’, *Marketing Science*, 31(6), pp. 900–912. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1287/mksc.1120.0727>.
- Mundaca, L. and Samahita, M. (2020) ‘What drives home solar PV uptake? Subsidies, peer effects and visibility in Sweden’, *Energy Research & Social Science*, 60, p. 101319. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101319>.
- Répartition par km²* (2023). Available at: <http://statistiques.public.lu/fr/recensement/repartition-par-km2.html> (Accessed: 25 March 2025).
- Ritchie, H., Roser, M. and Rosado, P. (2022) ‘Energy’, *Our World in Data* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://ourworldindata.org/energy> (Accessed: 12 June 2023).
- Rode, J. and Müller, S. (2021) ‘I Spot, I Adopt! Peer Effects and Visibility in Solar Photovoltaic System Adoption of Households’. Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3469548>.
- Skinner, A. and Jones, C. (2024) ‘Exploring the Spatial and Built Environmental Characteristics of Residential Solar Photovoltaic Implementations in Luxembourg’. *GISRUK Conference 2024*, Leeds: Zenodo, 10 April. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10926740>.
- Wang, Z. *et al.* (2022) ‘DeepSolar++: Understanding residential solar adoption trajectories with computer vision and technology diffusion models’, *Joule*, 6(11), pp. 2611–2625. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2022.09.011>.

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